

MODERN ROAD TRAFFIC SAFETY SYSTEM: STRUCTURE, SIGNIFICANCE AND DEVELOPMENT DIRECTIONS

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Abstract : This article presents an analysis of the social, legal and practical significance of the road safety system, as well as its structure and main tasks. The essence of the system, participating entities and their interaction, preventive and control mechanisms for ensuring safety are revealed. At the same time, proposals and recommendations are made to increase the effectiveness of the system.

Keywords : road safety, system, importance, essence, control, legal basis, cooperation, prevention, public policy.

Today, along with the rapid increase in the number of vehicles, the expansion of road infrastructure in urban and rural areas, and the increased mobility of the population, the number of road accidents and fatalities is also increasing significantly. This makes the issue of ensuring road safety a priority national problem for every country.

Ensuring road safety is an important condition not only for the protection of life and health of citizens, but also for the maintenance of legal order and social stability in society, and for sustainable economic development. After all, every road traffic accident causes significant damage not only to people's lives, but also to the state's economy.

This system consists of a complex of multifaceted and interrelated elements, in which the cooperation of state bodies, law enforcement agencies, civil society institutions and the public plays an important role. Therefore, a deep analysis of the nature of the road safety system, studying its legal bases, organizational-practical mechanisms and interaction of the participating subjects is one of the urgent tasks today.

According to I.A. Ivanov, the roads of the early period were divided into such types as " military (for troop movement) roads, trade roads, administrative roads (connecting administrative territorial units, intended for transporting spoils), roads used for the construction of structures, and internal city roads ¹. "

Although I.A. Ivanov's approach reflects historical reality, it may give the impression that roads were built solely for instrumental purposes. In fact, roads were also closely linked to the cultural, social, and geopolitical factors of civilization formation. Therefore, it is appropriate to view roads not only as a means of material movement, but also as an important component of the processes of cultural exchange, integration, and centralization between societies.

In addition, the issue of the road safety system is a complex issue at the intersection of the fields of law, transport logistics and public administration. A number of Russian and foreign scientists have expressed scientific doctrinal views in this direction. Below we will consider recognized scientists in this field and their views. In particular, V.N. Kurlyandsky interprets road safety as an integral part of state policy and emphasizes the need for a systematic approach in this area, and that safety is not only prevention, but also a combined mechanism of legal, organizational, technical and educational measures ².

V.N. Kurlyandsky's assessment of road safety as an integral part of state policy is an attempt to take this area out of the scope of ordinary administrative measures and raise it to the level of a strategic state goal. The author's view that safety should be viewed not only as prevention, but also as a combination of legal, organizational, technical and educational mechanisms clearly demonstrates the need for a comprehensive approach.

However, from this point of view, the question may arise: which of these mechanisms is the priority? For example, if the legal culture in society is low, technical and organizational measures may not be effective. From this point of view, some researchers (for example, R. Elvik) argue that ensuring security

¹ Ivanov I.A. Dorogi mira. Istoriya i sovremennost / " Infra-Engineering ", 2017. - 7 p.

²Kurlyandsky V.N. Pravovye osnovy obespecheniya bezopasnosti dorojnogo dvizheniya. Moscow: Yuridicheskaya literatura. – 2006. – P. 72-79.

requires dynamic and structural regulation depending on the situation.

Thus, although V. N. Kurlyandsky's approach is comprehensive and sets the main directions, in real practice a balanced management concept is required to ensure that all its elements work equally effectively.

According to V.P.Bakharev, it is proposed to organize the system of offenses in the field of traffic safety and its preventive mechanisms based on legal order, control, public involvement and technologies ³.

V.P. Bakharev puts forward a three-way approach to the effective organization of the traffic safety system: *legal mechanisms* - determining responsibility for traffic violations and implementing it within the law, *control institutions* - internal affairs bodies, JDYXB, video surveillance and patrol services, *public control and cooperation* - ensuring the active participation of citizens in understanding their rights and obligations.

In this approach, V.P. Bakharev's innovative approach is to emphasize the role of technology. Indeed, modern control technologies in the field of road traffic (AI, digital analytics, intelligent systems) increase the effectiveness of prevention.

V.P. Bakharev, V.N. Kurlyandsky and Rune Elvik are among the scientists who have put forward different scientific approaches to the issue of ensuring road safety. Each of them evaluates the safety system from different points of view and pays special attention to its main components.

Comparative analysis shows that while V.P. Bakharev's model is an approach based on legal, social and practical mechanisms, V.N. Kurlyandsky considers security as a system within the framework of a complex state policy. Rune Elvik focuses on analytical tools that serve to determine effectiveness. These different approaches serve as a theoretical and practical basis for a comprehensive coverage of the security system and the formation of its complete model.

V.D. Nazarov emphasized that the road safety system is "social security in the transport environment", which indicates its specific feature - the mass nature of

³ Bakharev V.P. Administrativno-pravovye osnovy obespecheniya bezopasnosti dorozhnogo dvizheniya. Moscow: Jurist . - 2009. - S. 47-56.

traffic and the high potential of the human factor ⁴.

This approach views road safety not only as a technical or legal issue, but as an integral part of the overall system of social relations in society.

An important point in the opinion of V.D. Nazarov is the decisive role of the human factor. In his opinion, ensuring safety in transport directly depends not only on legislation and technical means, but also on the behavior, culture and level of legal awareness of people. In this regard, V.D. Nazarov advocates the need to study transport safety in connection with the socio-psychological environment.

However, some researchers may consider this view to be too generalized. Because the concept of “social security” is broad and relative, which in practice can lead to certain uncertainties in the development of precise analysis and political and legal measures. Therefore, although V.D. Nazarov's approach can be an important philosophical basis for a comprehensive analysis, it requires coordination with legal, technical and organizational means to develop it as a practical system.

V.D. Nazarov interprets road safety in a broad social context, highlighting the human factor and the mass traffic environment as decisive factors. This view strengthens the role of socio-humanitarian approaches in ensuring safety, creating an opportunity to link legal and technical mechanisms with the general cultural and moral environment in society.

M.A. Fominykh emphasizes that "analysis and classification of traffic accidents are of great importance in the prevention of crimes and the legal regulation of traffic, and it is necessary to assess the security system in a dynamic manner ⁵. "

M.A. Fominykh places the methods of analysis and classification in the prevention of crimes related to road traffic accidents and the legal regulation of traffic in a central place in his scientific views. According to him, for the road

⁴Nazarov V.D. *Sotsialnye aspekty obespecheniya bezopasnosti dorozhnogo dvizheniya*. St. Petersburg: Nauka. - 2010. - S. 102-109.

⁵Fominykh M.A. *Analysis of road transport processes: legal and organizational aspects*. Yekaterinburg : UrFU. - 2012. - S. 17-26.

safety system to function optimally, it must be constantly assessed in a dynamic state, that is, organized as a system that can quickly and accurately adapt to changing situations.

This approach of M.A. Fominykh encourages the adoption of political and legal decisions through practice-oriented and result-oriented analysis. He justifies the need for statistical data, crime analysis, systematic study of crime cases and their trends in order to correctly formulate strategies and measures in the field of security. Thus, he sees the road safety system not as a static, but as a dynamic system that is reassessed in real time.

However, there are certain challenges in implementing this theory. For example, insufficient data collection for analysis and classification, poor information systems, or lack of human resources can negatively affect the effectiveness of this approach. It also requires appropriate institutions and a high level of expertise to make decisions based on the results of the analysis.

M.A. Fominykh's views emphasize the central role of scientific analysis, situation assessment and classification in road safety. In his opinion, ensuring safety is not a set of one-time measures, but an active management process based on constant analysis and adaptation. This approach serves as a theoretical and practical basis for implementing systemic and digital reforms in the field.

Peter R. Stopher, evaluating the relationship between transport and security as an "integrated transport policy", emphasized that road safety is not only a means of combating crime, but also a social guarantee of saving individual lives ⁶.

Australian researcher Peter R. Stopher approaches the issue of road safety from the perspective of transport policy and social justice. In his research, he evaluates safety not only as a means of reducing crime, but also as a social guarantee aimed at saving the lives of citizens. In his opinion, safety is a social function that should be guaranteed by the state, and its implementation should be ensured through an integrated transport policy.

⁶ Stopher, P.R., & Stanley, J. Introduction to Transportation Policy: A Public Policy View. Edward Elgar Publishing. - 2014. - P. 33-39.

Peter R. Stopher sees the elements of transport infrastructure, the legal framework regulating traffic, the movement culture of citizens, technical control means and education as a whole system in the formation of an integrated transport policy. In his opinion, managing these elements not separately, but in an interconnected manner, can bring the level of safety to a higher level.

The advantage of this approach is that it views security from the perspective of humanism and social justice. In Stopher's theory, the preservation of civilian life is a strategic task of the state. Therefore, he considers security to be a multidisciplinary policy implemented through education, propaganda, and the legal order. However, according to some critics, the decisive factor in implementing an integrated policy is institutional cooperation, financial capabilities, and political will. Otherwise, conceptual ideas may fail in practice.

In Peter R. Stopher's concept, road safety is not simply the fight against crime, but also respect for human life, social security, and state responsibility. His concept of "integrated transport policy" is an attempt to formulate safety not as a set of practical measures, but as part of a comprehensive state policy.

Rune Elvik developed statistical analysis and evaluation methods for road safety⁷, and his work served as the basis for setting European safety standards.

Renowned Norwegian researcher Rune Elvik is one of the scientists who developed empirical analysis and numerical assessment methods in the field of road safety. His research is known, in particular, for proposing the use of robust statistical models in the assessment of road accidents, and this approach served as a major source in the development of European safety standards.

Rune Elvik believes that to assess the effectiveness of a road safety system, it is necessary to collect reliable and objective data on various factors - the number of violations, deaths and injuries, traffic flow, quality of infrastructure, and the results of education and information campaigns. He considers the assessment of the effectiveness of safety policies through precise numerical indicators to be the

⁷ Elvik R. A comprehensive approach to evaluation of road safety policy. Traffic Safety Research . - 2024. - P. 23-29.

main criterion of a scientific approach.

Rune Elvik's models cover the stages of analysis, forecasting and political decision-making. That is why his methods are widely used in the development of state programs for road safety management in European countries. His theory allows us to find a clear and fact-based answer to the question "how well does safety policy work?" in practice.

However, according to some critical views, the statistical approach cannot always fully reflect the human factor, the behavior and culture of citizens. Also, an assessment based only on numbers risks not taking into account possible social factors. In addition, the institutional complexity of data quality assurance and real-time collection may affect the effectiveness of this model in practice.

Rune Elvik's research focuses on developing methods for assessing road safety on a scientific and empirical basis. His work provides objective analytical tools for determining the effectiveness and efficiency of safety policies. Elvik's model views safety not only as a preventive measure, but also as a field of rational management and strategic analysis.

Theoretical approaches to the issue of road safety put forward by various scientific schools and scholars demonstrate its complex, multifaceted and systemic nature. In particular, the conceptual approaches of such scholars as Rune Elvik, Peter R. Stopher, M.A. Fominykh and V.N. Kurlyandsky demonstrate the interrelationship of various scientific methodologies in ensuring road safety.

In general, the views of these scientists indicate the need for a comprehensive approach to the field of safety. Elvik and Fominykh promote numerical analysis and situation assessment methods, Stopher considers the preservation of human life to be the main goal, and Kurlyandsky advocates the formation of safety as a complex direction at the level of state policy. If all of these views are systematically combined, it will be possible to achieve high results in ensuring modern road safety.

Based on the above analysis, the road safety system can be scientifically defined as follows. *The road safety system* is a multi-stage and dynamic legal and

social system aimed at protecting human life, health and property, based on integrated cooperation between the legal awareness of road users, technical and information infrastructure, state governance institutions and public control, and aimed at ensuring a stable and predictable traffic environment through crime prevention, risk assessment and balanced management.

In this definition, we have expressed road safety not only in terms of legal and organizational aspects, but also in terms of scientifically based factors such as the human factor, analysis and statistical assessment, social guarantees and state policy, public participation and technology. Against the background of modern threats, increased traffic flow and urbanization, this system requires constant real-time analysis and adaptive management.

With the development of time, all countries began to have their own documents establishing traffic rules. These documents mainly reflected rules such as driving at intersections, reducing speed when approaching intersections, prohibiting overtaking on difficult sections of the road, the priority of pedestrians during movement, and the status of special ceremonies. For example, “ Emperor Peter I issued a decree in 1683 in Moscow prohibiting fast, unmanned movement, and driving according to the right-hand rule . ”⁸

In every country, traffic rules were created to meet common needs - maintaining traffic order, preventing collisions, and ensuring the safety of citizens. In historical sources, in particular, in the example of decrees from the time of Peter I, we can see that these rules began to take shape not as legal norms, but as norms of administrative and moral order.

The decree of Emperor Peter I in 1683 can be considered the first legal prototype of the modern "right-hand traffic rule." This historical fact indicates that traffic rules arose not primarily from legislation, but from the practical needs of state administration and maintaining public order.

Briefly, this information suggests that today's highly structured traffic laws are the product of centuries of experience, necessity, and statecraft evolution.

⁸Ivanov I.A., Dorogi mira. Istoriya i sovremennost/ "Infra-Engineering", 2017. - 9 p.

The invention of the automobile in the 19th century and its gradual introduction into society led to fundamental changes in the field of road traffic. In earlier times, the main means of transport were pulled by animals - horses, donkeys, camels, etc. These animals, according to their natural instincts, sensed danger and, in unexpected situations, took precautionary measures such as slowing down, stopping, or changing direction. Even when the driver of the cart did not sense danger, the animal's intuitive movements often prevented accidents. However, with the advent of self-propelled vehicles, this opportunity disappeared. Driving a car required not only driving skills, but also special knowledge, practical skills, and a certain amount of experience. At the same time, the need to introduce clear rules, road signs, and signals to ensure traffic safety on the roads became clear.

For the first time in France, modern traffic signs have been installed in three different versions on the streets of Paris, in order to quell the discontent among the population due to the increase in cars, the increase in traffic accidents, and to calm them down by installing signs that warn them of danger. They were as follows: "steep slope"; "dangerous turn"; "uneven road"⁹.

According to the information provided, this experiment in France, as the first form of a modern road sign system, is not only of historical significance, but is also seen as a legal and organizational response to the transport revolution taking place in society. This situation indicates that the popularization of vehicles in society requires not only economic or social changes, but also a renewal of legal-normative and moral-cultural relations.

Signs such as "steep slope", "dangerous turn" and "uneven road", first installed in Paris, were intended to ensure the physical characteristics of the roads and the safety of road users. These signs served to warn of danger in advance, coordinate traffic and create an atmosphere of trust among citizens. In this regard, these measures can also be considered as a means of satisfying the social demand of the population for safety, strengthening the legal position of the state in road

⁹ <https://circul.info/article/istoriya-dorozhnykh-znakov> (date of application 04/16/2025)

traffic and stabilizing public opinion.

It should be noted that the system of road signs was formed as an important element of "legal dialogue" between the society and the state, and its first examples became the main basis of today's complex road safety system.

The road safety system is a set of complex legal, organizational, informational and technical measures aimed at protecting the life, health and property of citizens in society, as well as regulating the movement of vehicles. We can classify this system on the basis of various scientific and legal criteria, through which its structure, tasks and practical mechanisms are more clearly manifested.

First, if we classify this system *by legal basis*, we see that it is provided for by constitutional, legislative and regulatory legal acts. For example, Articles 25-27, 48 and 54-56 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan¹⁰ stipulate that the life, health and safety of every person is guaranteed by the state. Also, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Road Traffic"¹¹, the Code of Administrative Responsibility¹² and Presidential Decrees, in particular, the Decree "On Approval of the Concept of Public Safety of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Measures for its Implementation"¹³ form the legal basis for ensuring road safety. These documents clearly define the procedure for interdepartmental cooperation, preventive work, control and responsibility.

Secondly, according to *its organizational structure*, this system includes the activities of multi-level institutions. At the central level, the Ministry of Internal Affairs, in particular, the Ministry of Internal Affairs, is the leading body. In

¹⁰ Uzbekistan Republic Constitution // Legislation information national base, 01.05.2023, 03/23/837/0241-issue // <https://lex.uz/docs/6445145>.

¹¹ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 19.01.2024 No. ZUR-900 "On Road Traffic" // National Database of Legislative Information, 20.01.2024, No. 03/24/900/0053; 07.02.2025, No. 03/25/1025/0116 / <https://www.lex.uz/docs/6764454>.

¹² Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Administrative Responsibility // Bulletin of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 1995, No. 3; National Database of Legislative Documents No. 03/25/1022/0083; 07.02.2025, No. 03/25/1024/0115; 07.02.2025, No. 03/25/1025/0116; 21.02.2025, No. 03/25/1033/0164; 21.02.2025, No. 03/25/1035/0166; 26.02.2025, No. 03/25/1038/0188; 03/03/2025, No. 03/25/1042/0212; 26.03.2025, No. 03/25/1050/0276. <https://lex.uz/docs/97664>.

¹³ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-27 dated 29.11.2021 "On approval of the Concept of Public Security of the Republic of Uzbekistan and measures for its implementation" // National Database of Legislative Information, 01.12.2021, No. 06/21/27/1116; 16.01.2024, No. 06/24/10/0031. <https://lex.uz/docs/5749291>.

addition, the Ministry of Emergency Situations, the Ministry of Health, the Ministry of Transport and the Highways Committee are also actively involved in this system. At the regional level, there are district and city IIB YHXB departments, security commissions under local governments. In addition, non-governmental organizations and public institutions participate in the system as partner entities.

Thirdly, according to functional areas, the road safety system is divided into prevention, control, response and infrastructure measures. In the field of prevention, measures are taken to increase legal culture among the population, provide children with car safety lessons, and work with the public. The tasks of control and detection of violations are carried out through video surveillance and intelligent radar systems. In response to incidents, ambulance, law enforcement agencies and medical institutions work together. Also, improving transport infrastructure, road signs and lighting are important tasks of the system.

Fourth, in the field of information and digital technologies, the road safety system is being enriched with intelligent transport systems. These systems include automated monitoring, "smart" traffic lights, pedestrian mobile applications and online information platforms. Digital tools are also widely used in the processes of automatic detection of data on violations, drawing up protocols and providing information to citizens.

It is a system of state and society that is integrated, based on a legal framework, equipped with technology, and prioritizes the interests of citizens. The effectiveness of this system depends on the organic cooperation, coordinated action, and result-oriented activities of each element.

Based on the content and legal classification of the traffic safety system, we can highlight its specific features.

We can conditionally show the specific features of the road safety system in the example of the following.

Firstly, the road safety system is a complex and multi-sectoral system. Road safety is a multi-sectoral system that includes not only the activities of law

enforcement agencies, but also activities in the fields of transport, healthcare, education, engineering and information. This system includes not only legal, but also technical and preventive mechanisms. In this regard, the road safety system is integrative and interdisciplinary, and its effectiveness directly depends on interdepartmental coordination.

secondly, the road safety system is directly based on inter-agency cooperation. The process of ensuring road safety involves the responsibility of several government agencies at the same time. Internal affairs authorities, transport authorities, local authorities, health and educational institutions, civil society and mass media all participate in this system as partners. Therefore, this system has a legal and organizational approach that requires functional cooperation and coordination.

Thirdly, legal norms in the field of road safety are introduced at different levels. The legal system of road safety is regulated by several levels of documents, such as laws, codes, resolutions, decrees, orders and methodological instructions. This forms its multi-level regulatory and legal nature. For example, the Law "On Road Traffic" establishes general norms, while the Code of Administrative Responsibility establishes liability for violations.

Fourth, road safety is one of the fastest-growing technologically advanced areas. The road safety system is closely linked to information technologies and intelligent management systems, and digitalization and automation processes are taking place in this area very actively. Technologies such as intelligent transport systems (ITS), automatic radars, video surveillance, and digital protocol creation are among the modern features of the system.

Fifth, one of the most important tasks in the road safety system is the prevention of road accidents. This prevention is carried out through measures such as increasing the legal culture of the population, conducting road safety training in educational institutions, and informing citizens through the mass media. In this regard, the road safety system relies not only on punishment, but also on prevention based on awareness and education.

Sixth , the road safety system has a mass character, affecting all segments of society. Road safety is a mass social phenomenon, affecting not only drivers or pedestrians, but also all citizens, business entities and state organizations using vehicles. This circumstance serves as the basis for characterizing this system as a system of universal social significance.

Seventh , there are many "invisible" factors in the field of road safety - human psychology, the ability to perceive danger, mass behavior, sense of speed, reaction time, and other physiological and social mechanisms. Their regulation through legal norms means that unconventional approaches are required in this system.

The road safety system is unique and has many specific features. Its legal, organizational and technological foundations need to be improved in accordance with modern requirements. In this system, it is important to ensure not only legal measures, but also education, prevention, technology and active participation of civil society.

The road safety system is a complex, multi-level, dynamic and integrated system aimed at protecting the lives, health and property of citizens in society, as well as regulating the movement of vehicles. It is based not only on a legal and normative basis, but also on theoretical and practical foundations in various fields, such as the human factor, education, psychology, engineering and digital technologies. Its historical evolution and modern international scientific approaches indicate that this system should be viewed not only as an administrative or technical process, but also as a socio-legal institution.

Based on the content of the concept, classification and specific features of the road safety system, it is appropriate to make the following scientific theoretical conclusions, proposals and recommendations:

Firstly , the road safety system is a multi- stage and dynamic legal and social system aimed at protecting human life, health and property, based on integrated cooperation between the legal awareness of road users, technical and information infrastructure, state governance institutions and public control, and aimed at

ensuring a stable and predictable traffic environment through crime prevention, risk assessment and balanced management.

secondly , we can classify the road safety system based on the following scientific and legal criteria:

- on legal grounds;
- according to the organizational structure;
- according to functional areas;
- according to the application of information and digital technologies in the field;
- developing a road safety system that is not only based on legal and control functions, but also in combination with education, information, enlightenment and technology.

thirdly , the following can be cited as specific features of the road safety system:

- the road safety system is a complex and multi-branch system;
- the road safety system is directly based on interdepartmental cooperation;
- legal norms in the field of road safety are introduced at different levels;
- ensuring road traffic safety is one of the technologically fast-changing areas;
- One of the most important tasks in the road safety system is the prevention of road accidents;
- the road safety system has a mass character affecting all layers of society;
- there are many “invisible” factors in the field of road safety – human psychology, the ability to perceive danger, public behavior, sense of speed, and physiological and social mechanisms such as reaction time;

Fourth , it is necessary to improve the regulatory and legal framework to ensure that the security sector is managed not only by one agency or state body, but also through interagency cooperation. For example, *a single coordinated legal mechanism* should be developed that would determine the algorithms for interaction between the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the Ministry of Emergency

Situations, the Ministry of Health, local khokimiyats, and civil society institutions. This would divide the tasks of the system, clarify responsibilities, and increase effectiveness.

fifthly , recognizing the decisive importance of the human factor in the effective management of the road safety system, special attention should be paid to increasing the legal culture of citizens, especially to the introduction of educational programs on car safety among young people and children. In this regard, it is recommended to widely introduce interactive training courses through mass media, educational institutions and Internet promotion.

